

Patient No.	sex	Age	Radiological Code	hospitalized days after operation	Hospitalized Span	If any, specified as	weight	height
1	Female	78		41	46			
2	Female	72	636624	11	20			
3	Male	76	788585	12	20		66	1.64
4	Female	75	39241	16	21			
5	Male	50	i100047983	14	22			
6	Male	54	1121178	14	21			
7	Female	65	i100098179	14	17			
8	Male	48	i100096044	11	13			
9	Male	63	1122813	16	21			
10	Female	80	i100103722	15	22			
11	Male	81	i100102498	19	24			
12	Male	71	1125844	11	26			
13	Male	47	1128344	11	14			
14	Male	75	1128749	15	22			
15	Female	72	1132883	11	17			
16	Female	58	1133172	23	33			
17	Male	69	1133220	13	33			
18	Male	65	1133274	11	15			
19	Male	57	i100105241	23	36			
20	Male	66	i100106158	25	29			
21	Male	61	1134095	13	19			
22	Male	67	1134094	17	23			
23	Male	56	i100103827	66	74		70	1.7
24	Male	62	1136082	17	21			
25	Female	81	1136272	22	25			
26	Female	61	1137595	13	17			
27	Female	55	i100112980	23	29			
28	Female	56	1140958	17	22			
29	Male	60	i100086795	15	20			
30	Male	61	1141370	18	23			
31	Male	53	1142236	24	31			
32	Female	54	1142563	10	12			
33	Male	59	1143928	9	16			
34	Male	55	1148679	10	19			
35	Female	79	i100112506	66	70			
36	Female	61	1150489	11	15			
37	Male	73	1151960	14	24		59	1.61
38	Male	55	1152149	12	19			
39	Male	78	i100114476	19	24		71	1.65
40	Female	31	R001155399	12	19		50	1.6
41	Male	90	1155404	24	40			

42 Male	62	i100116436	18	23	64	1.65
43 Male	62	1156290	14	20	61	1.73
44 Female	60	1158226	21	29	67	1.57
45 Male	41	1156962	16	23	60	1.72
46 Male	64	1159766	31	34		
47 Female	77	1160794	35	39	50	1.58
48 Male	67	1002866	28	36	48.5	1.71
49 Male	78	i100119527	12	19	64	1.67
50 Male	47	1165034	10	16		
51 Male	58	1165570	15	18	67	1.7
52 Male	64	i100122336	15	20	60	1.7
53 Male	63	1168767	14	22		
54 Female	58	1169075	12	14		
55 Male	44	1169407	120	127		
56 Male	55	1170314	14	17		
57 Female	74	1171153	17	21	60	1.58
58 Male	47	1171989	10	15		
59 Female	71	1171948	15	20		
60 Male	79	1172597	22	29	63	1.71
61 Female	52	1174138	13	18		
62 Male	75	i100117889	16	20	56	1.69
63 Female	28	1174283	11	16		
64 Female	64	1175545	30	36	56	1.57
65 Male	61	1176117	14	20		
66 Female	68	i100125706	47	59		
67 Female	49	1177474	21	32		
68 Male	62	1178893	12	17		
69 Male	60	i100129545	11	18		
70 Female	58	1182269	13	18	50	1.64
71 Male	69	1182968	12	19	67	1.68
72 Male	53	i100131336	15	18	84	1.71
73 Female	27	i100130102	12	19	58.5	1.62
74 Male	77	1180485	13	23	49	1.65
75 Female	65	1187431	15	30		
76 Male	78	637395	10	16	70	1.72
77 Male	52	1182228	11	17	84	1.74
78 Male	37	1189306	11	16		
79 Male	49	1190139	14	17		
80 Male	52	1190956	10	16	61	1.68
81 Male	60	968778	13	18	62	1.68
82 Male	46	1192115	11	15		

83 Female	60	230079	13	19		
84 Male	47	i100138050	13	19	76	1.73
85 Male	62	1196734	11	16		
86 Female	39	1123191	11	18		
87 Male	64	1198707	10	16		
88 Male	62	1201239	10	15		
89 Male	46	1203110	9	12		
90 Female	64	1204120	11	17		
91 Female	54	1206564	13	18		
92 Female	52	1206981	17	21		
93 Female	45	1207847	11	19		
94 Male	65	1208636	15	20		
95 Female	52	159802	13	20		
96 Male	65	1214874	12	15		
97 Female	40	1215175	16	19		
98 Female	75	1118639	8	17		
99 Male	52	i100000586	10	16		
100 Male	65	1220342	12	15		
101 Male	82	1221221	18	27		
102 Female	40	1220995	10	12		
103 Male	58	1222222	11	17		
104 Male	74	1222528	16	25		
105 Male	82	1223406	12	20		
106 Male	60	1223776	12	19		
107 Female	69	1223619	13	18		
108 Female	78	i100152134	15	23		
109 Female	50	1225062	16	19		
110 Male	53	1226503	29	36		
111 Male	71	1228530	12	20		
112 Male	61	1228786	15	20		
113 Female	73	1229966	20	25		
114 Female	66	1230269	11	20		
115 Female	58	i100159205	28	31		
116 Male	50	1233726	11	16		
117 Male	76	88668	12	17		
118 Female	63	1238110	15	20		
119 Male	48	1239830	14	18	75	1.72
120 Female	76	884144	35	38		
121 Male	59	1241366	13	18	75	1.76
122 Female	51	1243569	13	17		
123 Male	59	1243829	25	31		
124 Female	66	1245871	11	18	64	1.6
125 Male	61	1245909	11	16	66	1.72
126 Male	67	i100165224	12	19		
127 Male	36	i100169907	10	16	62	
128 Male	62		9	16		
129 Male	62	1252600	11	14		
130 Male	58	1253000	11	17		
131 Female	55	1252998	12	17		

132 Female	63	i100099212	15	21
133 Male	60	1255052	11	21
134 Male	48	1257560	13	16
135 Male	41	1259336	11	13
136 Male	74	1260432	9	17
137 Male	71	1260687	14	21
138 Male	54	1262040	11	17
139 Female	81	1265039	11	14
140 Female	55	67801	9	13
141 Male	59		11	17
142 Female	39	1268324	12	22
143 Female	72	1269134	11	17
144 Male	65	1269629	12	20
145 Male	76	1270429	10	16
146 Female	72		11	18
147 Male	44		13	17
148 Female	40		14	16
149 Female	67		12	15
150 Male	39		9	15
151 Male	43		13	17
152 Female	78		24	26
153 Male	44		9	14
154 Male	60		12	18
155 Male	54		9	16
156 Male	53		9	12
157 Male	72		10	14
158 Male	66		10	13
159 Male	40		12	15
160 Male	67		10	15
161 Male	52		9	14
162 Female	53		10	13
163 Male	78		17	38
164 Male	78		16	21
165 Female	62		11	15
166 Male	42		12	14
167 Female	37		12	18
168 Female	55		12	17
169 Male	72		18	25
170 Male	63		10	14
171 Male	72		13	17
172 Female	60		10	13
173 Male	74		28	42
174 Female	48		11	17
175 Male	64		9	14
176 Female	42		13	21

177 Male	73	26	30
178 Male	62	11	17
179 Male	62	10	16
180 Male	47	12	15
181 Male	58	10	17
182 Female	43	9	17
183 Male	60	12	18
184 Female	74	14	18
185 Female	84	10	18
186 Male	74	12	16
187 Male	55	11	20
188 Male	74	13	18
189 Male	66	23	28
190 Male	56	12	18
191 Male	62	15	21
192 Male	50	11	16
193 Male	56	15	20
194 Male	75	10	22
195 Female	34	8	14
196 Female	57	11	15
197 Male	53	8	12
198 Female	47	11	17
199 Female	43	11	14
200 Male	55	12	20
201 Male	51	11	18
202 Male	67	15	18
203 Male	64	11	14
204 Female	63	14	18
205 Female	57	11	16
206 Male	50	11	16
207 Male	50	14	21
208 Female	57	10	15
209 Male	78	16	21
210 Male	56	16	20
211 Male	52	10	16
212 Male	71	14	21
213 Male	56	9	14
214 Male	70	13	21
215 Male	74	12	22
216 Female	31	10	14
217 Male	61	12	18
218 Female	72	11	17
219 Female	45	11	14
220 Female	64	13	15
221 Male	74	24	30
222 Female	62	14	16
223 Male	61	15	21

224 Male	68	14	19
225 Male	60	13	15
226 Male	57	9	14

ALB	pre-alb	LY	Anemia	HB	MCV	MCH	MCHC	EOS
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40

255

1.61

124

87.9

29.8

339

0.2

40 291 1.83 140 92.2 31.9 346 0.28

42 425 1.58 141 88.1 31.2 354 0.02

NE	perioperative transfusion	If any, specified as	history	smoking	Excessive alcohol	Concomitant diseases
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3.65

No

No

No

2.95 no

No

No

No

2.7

no

no

no

Hyperlipemia	Hypertension	Hyperglycemia	DM	history of operation	weight loss	If any, specified as
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No

108/62

No

No

No

not obvious

No

130/80

No

No

No

not obvious

no

130/70

no

no

no

not obvious

operation	days of the operation after hospitalization	Surgeon	operation time consuming	Extent of operation	Lymph node dissection	Radical degree
	5	3	325	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	9	3	180	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	8	3	195	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	3	290	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	8	4	270	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	100	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	3	4	110	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	2	3	120	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	3	200	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	3	85	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	15	6	385	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	3	5	105	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	195	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	6	3	120	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	10	2	250	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	20	4	245	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	4	4	190	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	13	3	135	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	4	3	90	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	6	3	265	distal subtotal	D2	R2 (palliative)
	6	3	270	proximal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	8	3	300	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	4 Y		100	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	13 y		235	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	4	5	270	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	6	3	215	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	4	195	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	3	230	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	3	210	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	210	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	2	3	90	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	245	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	9	3	200	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	4	3	195	distal subtotal	D2	R2 (palliative)
	4	3	120	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	10	2	315	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	180	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	5	6	210	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	7	3	3	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
	6	3	295	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete resection with

5 Y		260	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with R0 (complete
6	2	160	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with negative margin
8	3	180	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	3	200	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R2 (palliative)
3	3	290	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
4	3	195	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
8	6	340	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	3	230	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6	3	90	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
3	5	210	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	5	220	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
8	6	180	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
2	3	305	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	3	270	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R1 (microscopic residual disease or
3	3	220	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
4	4	255	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	210	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	225	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7 L		225	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	220	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
4 L		420	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	270	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6 Y		250	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6	3	160	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
12	3	230	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
11	3	255	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	210	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	4	345	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	225	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	3	260	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
3 Y		270	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
7	4	195	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R2 (palliative)
10	3	270	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R1 (microscopic residual disease or
5	3	320	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6	5	340	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6	3	205	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	220	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
3	3	300	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
6	3	200	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	4	140	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
4	3	260	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with

6	3	185	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	195	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	75	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	285	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
6	3	145	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	230	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
3	3	165	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	195	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
5	4	100	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
4	3	140	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
8	3	270	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	4	210	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
7	3	240	total gastrectomy	D2	R2 (palliative)
3	3	190	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	235	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
9	3	430	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	295	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
3	4	150	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
9	3	220	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
2	3	150	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	180	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
9	3	85	total gastrectomy	D2	R2 (palliative)
8	3	290	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	200	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	250	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
8	3	270	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
3	3	225	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	240	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
8	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	225	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	270	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
9	3	195	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
3	3	135	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	300	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
5	3	315	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	330	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
4	3	255	gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	150	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	245	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
4	3	195	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
6	3	150	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	330	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	185	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	290	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
6	3	255	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	320	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
3	3	165	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	190	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	165	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
			gastrectomy	D2	resection with

6	3	330	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
			gastroctomy		resection with
10	3	185	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	220	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
2	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	3	135	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
7	3	210	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	3	150	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	300	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	300	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
6	3	265	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
10	3	300	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
8	3	230	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
6	3	265	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
7	3	275	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	225	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	270	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	225	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
2	3	305	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
5	3	260	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	3	255	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
7	3	220	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	230	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	260	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	255	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	180	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
5	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
5	3	225	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
21	3	240	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
5	3	230	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	4	265	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
2	4	365	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
6	5	255	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
5	3	230	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
7	3	290	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
4	3	265	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
4	3	315	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
3	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
14	3	405	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete
6	3	285	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
5	4	360	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastroctomy		R0 (complete
8	4	250	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
					R0 (complete

4	3	360	total gastrectomy	D2	R2 (palliative)
6	3	270	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
6	4	310	total gastrectomy	D2	resection with
3	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	210	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
8	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	200	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
4	3	285	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
8	3	180	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
4	3	280	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
9	3	290	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	4	250	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	345	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	220	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
6	3	260	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	315	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	400	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
12	3	250	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	240	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
4	3	220	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
4	3	190	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
6	3	210	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	240	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
8	3	335	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	190	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
3	3	335	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	220	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
4	3	255	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	380	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	380	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
7	3	255	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
5	3	260	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	345	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
4	3	280	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	230	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
7	3	315	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
5	3	270	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
8	5	255	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
10	3	220	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
4	3	245	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	270	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
6	3	190	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
3	3	400	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
2	3	230	distal subtotal	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	260	gastrectomy	D2	resection with
2	3	330	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete
6	3	240	distal subtotal	D2	resection with
			gastrectomy		

5	3	270	total gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
2	3	200	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with
5	3	245	distal subtotal gastrectomy	D2	R0 (complete resection with

Affiliated organs excision	If yes, specified as	Reconstruction of digestive tract	stapler or not	blood loss	tansfusion during operatin	Hypotension during the operation	If yes, specified as	Pathology
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	360	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	345	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	300	2U RBC			
No		Billroth I	Yes	50	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	345	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	475	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	425	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	450	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	155	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	145	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	325	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	450	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	150	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	400	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	375	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	350	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	875	5U RBCI			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	100	No			
Yes		Billroth I	Yes	475	2U RBC			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	350	No			
No		Billroth II	No	150	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	300	No			
No		Billroth II	Yes	2400	7U RBC+plasma40			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	125	No			
Yes		Roux-en-Y	Yes	655	2U RBC+plasma40			
Yes		Billroth I	Yes	125	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	100	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	155	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	200	3U RBC			
No		Billroth I	Yes	350	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	375	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	50	No			
Yes		Billroth I	Yes	450	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	75	No			
No		Billroth II	Yes	400	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	50	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	550	3U RBC+plasma30			
No		Billroth I	Yes	50	No			
No		Billroth I	Yes	350	No			
No		Roux-en-Y	Yes	300	No	90/56 once		
No		Billroth I	Yes	200	2U RBC			

No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	400	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	200	No
No	Billroth I	No	175	No
No	Billroth II	No	1000	4U
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	350	No
No	Billroth I	No	200	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	655	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	545	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth II	No	400	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	75	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	375	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	300	No
No	Billroth II	No	325	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	No
No	Billroth I	No	55	No
No	Billroth I	No	200	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	85	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	No	120	No
No	Roux-en-Y	No	125	3U
No	Billroth I	No	50	No
No	Roux-en-Y	No	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	400	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	150	No
No	Billroth I	No	400	Yes
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	300	No
No	Billroth I	No	350	3U RBC
No	Billroth I	No	100	3U
No	Billroth I	No	100	RBCbecause
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	300	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No

Yes	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	700	RBC+plasma 400ml
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	350	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	75	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	70	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	499	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	100	3U RBC because of
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	85	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	150	No
Yes	Billroth II	Yes	275	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	375	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	375	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	85	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	85	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	85	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	180	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	350	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	250	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	350	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	65	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	365	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	365	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	255	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	150	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	150	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	125	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	135	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	525	3U RBC+plasma30
No	Billroth I	Yes	400	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	400	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	295	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	300	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	305	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	45	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	315	No

No	Billroth I	Yes	45	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	65	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	395	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	95	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	335	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	65	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	410	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	265	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	495	2U RBC+plasma20
No	Billroth I	Yes	295	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	65	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	265	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	465	3U RBC+plasma30
No	Billroth I	Yes	265	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	2U RBC+plasma20
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	305	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	45	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	155	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	300	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	40	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	255	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	305	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	355	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	275	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	245	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	105	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	65	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	265	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	405	3U RBC
No	Billroth I	Yes	95	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	55	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	260	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	285	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	380	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	200	3U RBC+plasma30
No	Billroth I	Yes	285	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	75	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	310	No

No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	300	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	305	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	315	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	215	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	80	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	360	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	275	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	370	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	250	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	90	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	380	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	40	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	380	No
No	Roux-en-Y	Yes	370	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	80	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	400	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	410	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	380	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	80	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	80	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	380	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	110	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	390	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	410	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	400	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
No	Billroth I	Yes	410	2U RBC+plasma20
No	Billroth I	Yes	60	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	50	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	385	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	425	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	105	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	60	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	70	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	60	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	60	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	60	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	100	No
Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	750	3U RBC+plasma20
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	115	No

Yes	Roux-en-Y	Yes	80	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	80	No
Yes	Billroth I	Yes	75	No

gastric size	hyperplasia of the gastric anterior wall	Histologic type	Differentiation Grade	Borrmann's classification	Vessel invasion	Tumor size (mm)	Tumor position	Tumor location - Wall		
14*10	Yes	signet-ring cell tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	U	entire		
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G2	II (bordered)	No	6*4	M+L	posterior wall		
		adenocarcinoma signet-ring	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	lymphatic vessel	2*1.5	L	anterior wall		
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G1 (well differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	1.5	L	anterior wall		
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G2	II (bordered)	No	5	U+M	entire		
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G2	II (bordered)	No	blood vessel	Whole	posterior wall		
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	L	posterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G2	II (bordered)	No	L	posterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	U	anterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No	L	posterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	L	anterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	L	posterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	L	anterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	U	posterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G2	ulcerating III (invasive)	No	L	entire			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	U+M	anterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	U	anterior wall			
		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	lymphatic vessel	L	posterior wall			
		7*4		adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		U	posterior wall
				adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating V	No		U	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			(unclassified) II (bordered)	No	4*3	L	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No		U+M	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G2			III (invasive ulceration)	No		M	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G2			II (bordered)	No		L	anterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating II (bordered)	No		M+L	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating III (invasive)	No		M	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma signet-ring	G3 (poorly differentiated)			II (bordered)	No		M	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma cell tubular	G2			II (bordered)	No		L	anterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating III (invasive)	No		U	anterior wall		
adenocarcinoma papillary	GX (Grade cannot be determined)			V (unclassified)	No		L	anterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G2			III (invasive)	No		M+L	anterior wall		
adenocarcinoma signet-ring	G3 (poorly differentiated)			II (bordered)	No		L	entire		
adenocarcinoma cell tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			II (bordered)	No		M+L	entire		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			II (bordered)	No		L	posterior wall		
adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)			ulcerating III (invasive)	No	3*2.5	L	posterior wall		
others	GX (Grade cannot be determined)			V (unclassified)	No		L	posterior wall		
11*9				mucinous adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	7*6	L	posterior wall
19*12	Yes	adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	6*2	M+L	posterior wall		
		adenocarcinoma signet-ring cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No		M+L	entire		

21*11	signet-ring cell adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	6*3	U+M	posterior wall
24*20	adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	1.5	U	anterior wall
15*9	adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	8*5	L	anterior wall
15*9	adenocarcinoma papillary	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	5*3	L	posterior wall
11*6	adenocarcinoma papillary	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	4*3	M+L	posterior wall
14*11	adenocarcinoma papillary	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	3.2*3	U	anterior wall
13*10	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4.5*3	L	posterior wall
12*8	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G1 (well)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	2*1	M+L	anterior wall
12*4	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	5	L	posterior wall
	others	(undifferentiated)	V (unclassified)	No	0.5*0.5	L	anterior wall
	signet-ring cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	lymphatic vessels	5	L	posterior wall
	signet-ring cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4	L	anterior wall
10*8	signet-ring cell tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	0.5	M+L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	lymphatic vessels	5	M+L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	4*3	M+L	posterior wall
9*8	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	4.5*3.5	U	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma papillary	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	7	M+L	posterior wall
10*8	adenocarcinoma signet-ring cell	(moderately differentiated) G4	V (unclassified)	No	1.5*0.8	M+L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	0.8*0.6	L	anterior wall
10*6	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G2	V (unclassified)	No	3*3	U	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	no	5	U	entire
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G1 (well)	V (unclassified)	No	6	L	posterior wall
	others	(undifferentiated)	V (unclassified)	No	2	L	posterior wall
	tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No	6	U	anterior wall
17*5	adenocarcinoma mucinous	G1 (well differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	4.5*4	L	posterior wall
15*6	adenocarcinoma tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	2.5*2.5	L	posterior wall
9*4	adenocarcinoma tubular	G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	2*1.5	L	posterior wall
12*7	signet-ring cell tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	lymphatic vessels	4*3	L	anterior wall
16*16	adenocarcinoma papillary	G1 (well differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	12*5.5	L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G2	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	U	anterior wall
7*5	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	1.5*1	L	posterior wall
14*12	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	2	L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	3	M+L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	2	M+L	anterior wall
14*10.5	adenocarcinoma tubular	(moderately differentiated) G3 (poorly)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	8*6	L	posterior wall
12*6.2	adenocarcinoma signet-ring cell	(moderately differentiated) G2	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	1.5*1.5	M+L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma signet-ring cell	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	2.5	M+L	posterior wall

14*6	tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		3	L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	5*4		M	posterior wall
	tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	5*4		L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		3	M+L	anterior wall
	others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No				
	tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		3	L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		1.5	M+L	posterior wall
	tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No	3*4		U+M	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	3*4		L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		4	U+M	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		5	L	posterior wall
	cell	G2 (moderately differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		1	L	posterior wall
	others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No	7*6		U	anterior wall
	tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		3	L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		3	L	anterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulcerating)	No		4	L	anterior wall
	cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		1	L	anterior wall
	others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		1	L	anterior wall
	others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		1	L	anterior wall
	others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		1	L	anterior wall
	tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		6	L	entire
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		3	L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	L	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	lymphatic vessel		6	U+M	entire
	cell	G1 (well differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		1	M+L	posterior wall
	others	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	M	posterior wall
	signet-ring	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		3	U+M	entire
	cell	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		4	M+L	entire
	tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		3	M	posterior wall
	adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No		2	U+M	entire
	adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No		2	U+M	entire
	adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	6*5		M+L	posterior wall
	signet-ring	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	5*6		M+L	posterior wall
cell	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	10*7		U+M	entire	
tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		2	M+L	anterior wall	
others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		5	M+L	anterior wall	
tubular	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	10*7		M+L	anterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		4	U+M	entire	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No		2	M+L	posterior wall	
cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	6*5		U	posterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		10	M	posterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No	5*4		L	posterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	IV (diffusely infiltrating)	No	10*8		L	posterior wall	
cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	blood vessel	10*8		L	entire	
cell	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	blood vessel		5	U	anterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	1.5*1		U	anterior wall	
ma	(moderately differentiated)	lesion)	No	4*3.5		U	anterior wall	
tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	4*3.5		L	anterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	4*3.5		L	anterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		2	M	anterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		1	M+L	posterior wall	
cell	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		3	M+L	posterior wall	
mucinous	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No		3	M+L	posterior wall	
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No		1	M+L	posterior wall	
others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		1	M+L	posterior wall	

tubular	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		4	M	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		4	U+M	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		4	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	2*3		M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	No	2*3		M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating)	No	6*4		M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	V	No	5*4		M+L	anterior wall
others	(poorly differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		1.5	M+L	anterior wall
others	(poorly differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		0.5	U	anterior wall
signet-ring	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		1.5	M+L	anterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		2	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	U	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		2	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		0.8	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		1	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		1	M+L	anterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		3	M+L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		3	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	/mphatic vessel	6*4		M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	/mphatic vessel		3	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		7	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		2	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No	1.5*1		M+L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		2*2	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		2*2	M+L	anterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		5*4	M+L	anterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		5*4	M+L	anterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		8*6	M+L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	V	No		8*6	M+L	posterior wall
others	(moderately differentiated)	(unclassified)	No		0.8	M	anterior wall
mucinous	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	/mphatic vessel		2.5	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	ulcerating	No	6*8		M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	blood vessel		2.5	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No	7*6		M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		3	U+M	entire
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	ulceration	No		1.5	L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		1.5	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(moderately differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		2	U+M	anterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		2	U+M	anterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		4	M+L	posterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		4	M+L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		1.5	L	posterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		1.5	L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		8	M	entire
signet-ring	(moderately differentiated)	ulcerating	No		8	M	entire
cell	(poorly differentiated)	II (bordered)	No		2.5	L	posterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		2.5	L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulcerating	No		4	U	posterior wall
mucinous	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	blood vessel		4	U	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	blood vessel		6	M+L	posterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	blood vessel		7	M+L	entire
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		7	M+L	entire
tubular	(moderately differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		5	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		5	M+L	posterior wall
signet-ring	(poorly differentiated)	III (invasive)	No		5	L	posterior wall
cell	(poorly differentiated)	ulceration	No		7	M+L	entire

signet-ring cell tubular adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	blood vessel	6	U	entire
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4	U	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	7*6	U+M	posterior wall
signet-ring cell tubular adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	4*5	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	4	U+M	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	4	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	2	M+L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	6	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	5	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No	2	L	anterior wall
others mucinous adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	(unclassified) III (invasive ulceration)	No	0.5	U	anterior wall
signet-ring cell others mucinous adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	(unclassified) III (invasive ulceration)	No	2	L	anterior wall
others mucinous adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	(unclassified) III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	U	entire
others mucinous adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	(unclassified) III (invasive ulceration)	No	1	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	5	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	2	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	2	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	2	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	2	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	1.5	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	4	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	blood vessel	4	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	2*1.5	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	U	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	8	M+L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	I (polypoid or fungating) II (bordered)	No	3	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	6	M+L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	/mphatic vessel	6*5	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	5	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	2	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	4	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	3	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	II (bordered ulceration)	No	4	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	V (ulceration)	No	1	L	posterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	(unclassified) III (invasive ulceration)	No	1	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	3	L	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	5	L	entire
adenocarcinoma	G3 (poorly differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	2	U	anterior wall
adenocarcinoma	G2 (moderately differentiated)	III (invasive ulceration)	No	5	L	entire

mucinous	G2	III (invasive	blood vessel	2	U	anterior wall
adenocarcino	(moderately	ulceration)				
mucinous	G2	III (invasive	No	2.5	L	anterior wall
adenocarcino	(moderately	ulceration)				
mucinous	G2	III (invasive	No	3	L	anterior wall
adenocarcino	(moderately	ulceration)				

Tumor location - Curvature	Tumor location - Invasion	pTNM stage (NCCN)	Tumor invasion depth (T)	Regional Lymph node (N)	Total number of dissected LN	Total number of positive LN	No.1	No.1
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0		
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	23	4		
curvature	no	IIIB	T4	N1	31	3		
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	29	2		
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	23	0		
entire	no	IIIB	T4	N1	16	5		
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2		
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0		
lesser	no	IIIA	T4	N0	29	0		
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	30	0		
lesser	no	II	T2	N1	22	4		
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	4		
lesser	no	IIIB	T3	N1	26	2		
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	17	0		
greater	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2		
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	17	0		
entire	no	IB	T2	N0	20	0		
lesser	no	II	T2	N1	29	4		
curvature	no	IIIB	T4	N0	16	6		
lesser	no	II	T2	N1	15	3		
curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	31	16		
greater	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0		
curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	20	0		
lesser	no	IV	T3	N3	31	15		
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	19	2		
lesser	no	II	T3	N0	27	0		
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N0	38	0		
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	34	3		
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	31	8		
lesser	no	II	T3	N0	16	0		
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	16	0		
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	36	0		
lesser	no	IIIB	T3	N2	18	8		
curvature	no	IIIA	T2	N2	32	8		
entire	no	IV	T3	N3	20	20		
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	35	0		
curvature	no	IIIA	T2	N2	17	11		
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	40	0		
curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	16	15		
lesser	no	IV	T4	N2	21	11		
curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	38	24		

lesser curvature	no	IV	T4	N3	24	18
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	35	4
lesser curvature	no	II	T3	N0	38	0
lesser curvature	duodenum invasion	IV	T4	N2	22	9
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	17	5
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0
greater curvature	no	II	T2	N1	18	4
lesser curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	15	0
entire	no		T3	N0	39	0
lesser curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	19	0
lesser curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	20	0
lesser curvature	no	IV	T4	N2	19	7
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	27	0
entire	duodenum invasion	IIIB	T4	N1	15	6
lesser curvature	no	II	T3	N0	15	0
greater curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	28	0
lesser curvature	no	IV	T4	N2	20	0
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	16	4
lesser curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	18	0
lesser curvature	no	II	T3	N0	20	0
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	31	0
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	53	0
lesser curvature	no	IB	T1	N1	27	3
greater curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	18	0
lesser curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	23	21
lesser curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	40	10
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	31	0
lesser curvature	no	IIIB	T4	N1	27	2
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	23	5
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	21	6
lesser curvature	no	II	T2	N1	15	3
lesser curvature	duodenum invasion	IV	T4	N1	31	3
lesser curvature	duodenum invasion	IIIA	T4	N0	24	0
greater curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	29	0
lesser curvature	no	II	T2	N1	15	3
lesser curvature	no	II	T2	N1	15	1
lesser curvature	no	IA	T2	N0	38	0
lesser curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	28	0
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	22	1
lesser curvature	no	II	T2	N1	13	1
greater curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	27	0

lesser						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N2	22	12
lesser	no	IIIB	T4	N1	27	0
curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	23	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	19	0
curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	28	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0
curvature	no	IIIA	T4	N0	42	0
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	31	8
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	24	2
lesser	no	IIIB	T3	N2	34	12
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	19	0
greater	no	IV	T4	N3	26	20
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	25	5
curvature	no	IIIB	T4	N1	18	0
lesser	no	IV	T3	N3	24	18
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	27	0
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	29	0
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	27	0
entire	no	II	T3	N0	27	0
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	25	2
curvature	no	II	T2	N0	24	0
lesser	no	IV	T4	N3	38	30
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	26	0
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	15	0
lesser	no	II	T3	N0	15	0
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	15	0
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	26	0
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	36	3
lesser	no	IIIA	T1	N0	28	0
curvature	no	IIIA	T1	N0	18	0
lesser	no	IV	T4	N3	20	16
curvature	no	IV	T3	N2	25	8
lesser	no	IV	T3	N2	25	8
entire	no	II	T3	N0	41	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	14	0
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	0
lesser	no	IIIA	T4	N0	16	0
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	22	0
entire	no	IB	T2	N0	17	0
lesser	no	IB	T2	N0	17	0
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N1	28	2
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	29	2
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	39	6
lesser	no	IB	T2	N0	27	0
curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	27	0
entire	no	II	T3	N0	14	0
lesser	no	IB	T2	N0	25	0
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	34	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	21	0
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	21	0
lesser	no	IIIA	T2	N2	37	7
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	19	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	20	0
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	20	0
lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	32	3
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	21	0
lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	21	0

greater	no	II	T3	N0	22	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIB	T4	N1	34	3
curvature lesser	no	II	T1	N2	31	0
curvature lesser	no	II	T3	N0	27	0
curvature lesser	duodenum	II	T2	N1	17	1
curvature lesser	invasion	IA	T1	N0	29	2
curvature lesser	no	IIIB	T3	N2	21	12
curvature lesser	no	II	T2	N1	27	1
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	46	0
curvature lesser	no	IB	T1	N1	16	2
curvature lesser	no	IB	T1	N1	22	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	35	4
curvature lesser	no	IB	T2	N0	16	0
curvature lesser	no	IB	T2	N0	16	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	27	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	16	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	19	0
curvature greater	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2
curvature lesser	no	IV	T3	N3	21	16
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T2	N2	40	10
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T4	N0	17	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	31	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIB	T3	N2	22	10
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	17	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	78	0
curvature lesser	no	II	T3	N0	16	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T4	N0	22	0
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	15	0
curvature lesser	no	II	T2	N1	30	1
curvature lesser	duodenum	IIIB	T4	N1	15	5
curvature lesser	invasion	IIIA	T3	N1	21	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	30	2
curvature entire	no	II	T2	N1	36	3
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	26	0
curvature lesser	no	II	T2	N1	16	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIA	T3	N1	22	1
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	42	0
curvature entire	no	IV	T3	N3	67	32
curvature lesser	no	IA	T1	N0	22	0
curvature lesser	no	II	T3	N0	21	0
curvature lesser	no	IIIB	T4	N1	15	1
curvature entire	duodenum	IIIB	T4	N1	46	2
curvature greater	invasion	IV	T3	N3	23	16
curvature lesser	no	IB	T1	N1	34	2
curvature entire	no	IIIB	T4	N1	16	4

entire	esopnagus	IV	T4	N2	20	16
greater	invasinn					
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	24	3
lesser						
curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	24	15
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	22	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	29	7
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	16	1
entire	no	IB	T2	N0	24	0
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	17	0
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	16	0
entire	no	IIIB	T3	N2	43	10
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	19	1
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	29	1
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	30	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IB	T1	N1	16	3
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	4
lesser	no	IB	T1	N1	28	3
curvature	duodenum					
entire	invasinn	II	T3	N0	23	0
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	28	4
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	17	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	26	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	28	0
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	15	2
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	39	12
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	26	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	15	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IV	T4	N2	22	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	22	9
lesser						
curvature	no	IB	T2	N0	32	0
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	15	0
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T3	N0	29	0
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	35	6
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	15	0
greater	no	II	T3	N0	17	0
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N2	24	13
entire	no	IIIB	T3	N2	15	11
lesser						
curvature	no	II	T2	N1	26	1
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	28	1
entire	no	IIIA	T3	N1	29	1
lesser						
curvature	no	IIIB	T3	N3	33	30
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	30	0
lesser						
curvature	no	IA	T1	N0	29	0
greater						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	27	2
entire	no	IIIB	T4	N1	34	2
greater						
curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	15	2
entire	no	IA	T1	N0	27	0

greater curvature	no	IV	T3	N3	29	21
greater curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	28	1
lesser curvature	no	IIIA	T3	N1	31	2

M0	No
M0	No
M0	No

sandostat in	ambroxol	liquid diet	TPN/EN	Duration fo the TPN/EN	gastric tube	post- operative transfusio n	If any, specified as	compliacat ion
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no

11 TPN

11d

4d

No

0.1 q8h*6d

8d

TPN

8d

4d

No

bleeding	infection	MODS	leak	thrombolysis	SIRS	SIRS duration	death	gastric stump
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No
No
No
No

diagnosis of anatomy

Yes
Yes
Yes

pulmonary

No
No
No

Yes 2

No
No

Yes 4

Yes

No
No

diagnosis

No
No

No
No

Yes 4

diagnosis

diagnosis

pulmonary

No
No
No
No
No
No
No
No

No
No

No
No

No
No

No
No

No
No

Yes 3

No
No

Yes 3

Yes 2

diagnosis

No
No

Yes

Yes 5

No
No

pulmonary
fever

No
Yes

Yes 4

ACF

No
No
No
No
No
No
Yes 4
No
Yes 6
No
No
No
No
No
Yes 2
No
No
Yes 6
No
No
No
No
No
Yes 8
Yes 4
No
No
No
Yes 10
Yes 4
No
Yes 4

unknow

No

enema*3d

No

pulmonary

No

No

No

No

Yes 6

Yes 3

No

No

No
No
No
No
Yes 5
No
No
No
No
Yes 6
No
Yes 5
No
Yes 4
No
Yes 4
No
Yes 3
Yes 6
No
Yes 3
No
No
No
Yes 3
No
Yes 3
Yes 5
Yes 6
No
No
No
No
Yes 4
No
No
No
Yes 7
Yes 5
No
Yes 3
No
No

No

No

No